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2. Rakhmonov Sunnatillo Mavlonovich INTERPRETATION A PERFECT HUMAN IN THE TARIKATS MAWLAWI AND NAQSHBANDI.....	13
3. Samadov Aktamkul Rafikovich UNITY OF MORALITY AND AESTHETICS IN PERSONAL MIND: PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS.....	19
4. Abdumajidova Hamida IMPACT OF MODERNIZATION OF THE CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES ON THE ACTIVITY OF SOCIO-POLITICAL RELATIONS.....	26
5. Бегматова Мўътабар Аскарловна, Усанов Равшан Тураявич МАДАНИЯТШУНОСЛИК ФАНИГА ЯНГИЧА ЁНДАШУВ.....	30
6. Боймуродов Зоҳид Шокирович ”ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИ” КАТЕГОРИЯСИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЭКСПЛИКАЦИЯСИ.....	35
7. Жураева Дилафруз Жамуродовна “БОБУРНОМА” – ТАБИАТ ЭСТЕТИКАСИНИНГ ИЛК МАНБАСИ СИФАТИДА.....	44
8. Отабаев Икромжон Усмонжанович ТАРИХИЙ ОНГ ВА ТАРИХИЙ ХОТИРАНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ЗАРУРИЯТИ.....	52
9. Isomiddinov Yuldash Yusubboevich THE SOCIAL PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF ABDURAUF FITRAT’S SPIRITUAL HERITAGE.....	58
10. Кузиев Нодир Абдусалимович ИПАК ЙЎЛИ ДОИРАСИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ САВДО-ИҚТИСОДИЙ СОҲАЛАРИДАГИ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТЛАРИ.....	65
11. Мавлонов Илхомжон Холмирзаевич ЯНГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА МИЛЛИЙ ЮКСАЛИШНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ҲОЯВИЙ АСОСЛАРИ.....	70
12. Султонова Светлана Юриевна ГЛОБАЛЛАШУВ ШАРОИТИДА ТЕРРОРИЗМ ТАҲДИДЛАРИДАН ШАХСИЙ ЎЗИНИ-ЎЗИ ҲИМОЯ ҚИЛИШ МУАММОЛАРИ.....	75
13. Сўфиев Абдуҳаким Абдулазизович ТАДБИРКОР ШАХС ҲУҚУҚИЙ МАДАНИЯТИ ОШИРИШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.....	82

14. Туробов Бекпулат Нусратуллаевич ШАРҚШУНОС Е.Э. БЕРТЕЛЬС МУТАФАККИР АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ ИЖОДИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ ТЎҒРИСИДА.....	92
15. Турсунова Лайло ЁШЛАР МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИНИ ЮКСАЛТИРИШНИНГ ОБЪЕКТИВ ВА СУБЪЕКТИВ ОМИЛЛАРИ.....	97
16. Uzakova Lola Abdurashitovna THE STUDY OF PHILOSOPHICO-THEORETICAL VIEWS OF ALISHER NAVOI.....	103
17. Юсупова Феруза Зойировна АХЛОҚИЙ ТАФАККУР РИВОЖЛАНИШИДА ҚАДРИЯТ ВА ИДЕАЛ ТУШУНЧАЛАРИНИНГ ЎЗАРО НИСБАТИ.....	109
18. Maxmudova Aziza BIOETIKA ZAMONAVIY MADANIYATDA INDIVIDUALLIKNI HIMOYA QILISH SHAKLI SIFATIDA.....	115
19. Sayidov Qahramon O'ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSION RIVOJLANISH (MILLIY VA UMUMBASHARIY XUSUSIYATLAR).....	122
20. Махмудова Азиза, Афанасьева Олеся, Камариддинзода Аминабону ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО МИРОВОЗРЕНИЯ И ЦЕННОСТЕЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ВУЗА.....	127
21. Ҳамроев Саиджон ИНСОНИЯТ ТАФАККУРИ ТАРИХИДА ИЖТИМОИЙ АДОЛАТ МАСАЛАСИ ТАҲЛИЛИ (Платон ва Аристотель қарашлари мисолида).....	136
22. Шарипов Абдухакимжон ЎЗБЕК ФАЛСАФАСИ ВА ТАРАҚИЁТ СТРАТЕГИЯСИ УЙҒУНЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ.....	142
23. Асатуллоев Иномжон Абобакир ўғли ШАРҚ ВА ҒАРБ ФАЛСАФСИДА ИНСОН ҚАЛБИ ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ ҚАРАШЛАРНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШ ДИАЛЕКТИКАСИ.....	150

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Mazkur maqolada Alisher Navoiyning falsafiy-nazariy qarashlarining o'rganilishi aks ettirilgan. O'zbek va forsiy tillarda mukammal ijod qilgan Navoiy o'z asarlarida komil inson masalsiga alohida e'tibor qaratgan. Shu sababli, Navoiy merosining yosh avlodning ma'naviy kamol topishidagi o'rni beqiyosdir. Alisher Navoiy mashhur dostonnavis mutafakkir sifatida dong taratgan alloma bo'lib, undan jami oltita katta doston meros qolgan. Alisher Navoiyning ma'naviy ustozlari tasavvuf olamida insoniyat taraqqiyoti taraqqiyotiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan allomalar bo'lib, ularning faoliyati bevosita mutafakkirning o'zini ham ilhomlantirgan.

Kalit so'zlar: "Nasoyim ul muhabbat men shamoyim ul-futuvvat", "Tarixi muluki ajam", "Saddi Iskandariy".

ABSTRACT

This article reflects the study of philosophico-theoretical views of Alisher Navoi. Navoi, who is fluent in Uzbek and Persian, pays special attention to the issue of the ideal person in his works. Therefore, the role of Navoi heritage in the spiritual development of the younger generation is invaluable. Alisher Navoi was a famous poet and thinker, from whom a total of six great epos were inherited to present time. Alisher Navoi's spiritual teachers were scientists who made a great contribution to the development of mankind in the world of mysticism, and their work directly inspired the thinker himself.

Key words: "Nasoim ul muhabbat men shamoyim ul futuvvat", "Tarixi muluki ajam", "Saddi Iskandariy".

Introduction

The development of science, literature, and art that emerged in the XV-XVI centuries, as a period of a new awakening in the history of Movarounnahr, and in other areas began to manifest itself in comprehensive development and changes. During this period, literary and philosophical life developed mainly in the cities of Herat, Samarkand, Tabriz and Bukhara, and in each of these cities there were centers of knowledge and enlightenment. Such thinkers as Mavlono Abdurakhman Jami and Alisher Navoi, who were the founders of the Herat school, made a great contribution to the development of Persian-Tajik and Turkic-Uzbek literature.

Such unique scientists of our motherland have gained fame among the peoples of the world thanks to their huge scientific heritage. One of such universal thinkers is Alisher Navoi. Alisher Navoi

is not only a great thinker, but also the sultan of gazelles. The period of Alisher Navoi's life coincided with the period of the Timurid Renaissance, and the works of the thinker were considered a unique pearl of their time. Navoi, who is fluent in Uzbek and Persian, paid special attention to the issue of the ideal man in his works.

That is why young scientists from different cities and regions rushed to study with Alisher Navoi. The popularity of Samarkand and Bukhara, Tabriz and Herat in the XV-XVI centuries was closely connected with the activities of the people who worked there.

Military conflicts and the occupation of Khorasan by the Shaybanids had a significant impact on science and education, as well as other socio-economic changes that forced many scientists to leave their cities and move to cities such as India, Samarkand and Bukhara.

Research Methodology

Although Alisher Navoi wrote his first poems in his young age, he focused on the problem of the ideal person. He also tried to portray his friend Hussein Boykaro, one of the Timurid rulers, as a symbol of perfection. Indeed, Navoi's poem "Hilalia" is dedicated to Hussein Boikaro, in which Hussein Boikaro is embodied as a "just king" who raised the banner of justice high. [1. Б. 147]

After Alisher Navoi became an official during the reign of Hussein Baykaro, he built many buildings, madrassas and hospitals, mosques and bridges in Herat and Khorasan at his own expense. According to sources, Navoi has built more than three thousand buildings, which is an example of his concern for people. As Prime Minister, Alisher Navoi is known as a true patron of culture and art. His efforts to address socio-political issues correctly, treat all social strata of society equally, and pay special attention to non-discrimination issues began to be highly appreciated by his contemporaries.

The multifaceted scientific and theoretical heritage of Alisher Navoi, along with socio-political life, covers almost all topical issues of his time and provides a socio-philosophical analysis. As a philosopher and poet, Alisher Navoi in his views reflected on the problems of being, the philosophy of life, the meaning of life and human perfection. At the same time, as a statesman, Navoi in his works philosophically and artistically described the will of the people, their problems and aspirations, the activities of religious scholars, the way of life of kings and their duties to the people, based on historical examples.

The Naqshbandi teaching flourished during the time of Alisher Navoi. The development of the Naqshbandi teaching as a mystical teaching and its rise to the level of "state ideology" is closely connected with the activities of the most prominent murshids of the Naqshbandi teaching of the XV century, Abdurakhman Jami and Khoja Ubaidullah Ahror. Alisher Navoi, Hussein Baykara and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, the most prominent figures of that time, were among those who widely promoted Naqshbandiya and followed his teachings.

Alisher Navoi's spiritual teachers were scientists who made a great contribution to the development of mankind in the world of mysticism, and their work directly inspired the thinker himself. In particular, the ideas of Jalaleddin Rumi, Bahauddin Naqshband, Fariduddin Attar and Abdurakhman Jami had a great influence on the formation of the philosophical outlook of Alisher Navoi. Alisher Navoi studied the idea of the perfect man in the spiritual heritage of these thinkers, and enriched the interpretation of the perfect man in his works with high artistic coloring, became a model of perfection.

Influenced by the famous "Hamsa" of Nizami Ganjavi, one of the founders of the literature of the Eastern Renaissance, Alisher Navoi created "Hamsa" using the same plots and images, but with ideal dreams, ideas and creative atmosphere of the new century. Alisher Navoi is the greatest author of "Hamsa" after Nizami Ganjavi, as well as the first author to write "Hamsa" in the Turkic language. Alisher Navoi once again gave the heroes of Nizami Ganjavi the right to live in the Turkic world once again.

Alisher Navoi, interpreting the problem of the ideal person, says that in order to achieve happiness, a person must work and master some profession. According to Islamic teaching, although everything in this mortal world is ordained by God, Navoi explains that a person can improve by his own work and become a perfect person serving the interests of society. [2. Б. 112].

Analysis and results

Alisher Navoi received his Naqshbandi teachings under the guidance of his teacher and friend Abdurakhman Jami, and his in-depth study of the views of Fariduddin Attar from childhood served as the basis for his support of the Naqshbandi teachings. This is due to the fact that the teaching of Naqshbandi is reflected in the works of Alisher Navoi, and the main ideas of Naqshbandi are reflected in the works of Navoi.

In the works of Abdurakhman Jami, the four principles of the mystical Naqshbandi teachings were set forth: "xilvat dar anjuman" (loneliness in society), "nazar bar qadam" (attention to everything), "safar dar vatan" (journey to the motherland), "hush dar dam" (enjoy every moment). In the interpretation of Alisher Navoi, these principles are recognized as a sign of human behavior, his spirituality, keeping up with the times. The main emphasis in Navoi's work was on putting the interests of the people first in state policy.

Alisher Navoi in his work "Nasoim ul-muhabbat" gave a wide place to Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband, and in the epic "Hayrat ul-abror" also reflected the praise of Bahauddin Naqshband. From here it can be seen that Alisher Navoi was not only a staunch supporter of the teachings of Bahouddin Naqshbandi, but also an enlightened propagandist of the Naqshbandi teachings. In addition, many Navoi poems and the epic "Hamsa" comment on ideas consonant with the beliefs of Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband.

Alisher Navoi was a famous poet and thinker, from whom we inherited a total of six great epics. These are five epics that make up the famous Hamsa: "Hayrat ul-abror", "Farhod va Shirin", "Layli va Majnun", "Sabai Sayyor", "Saddiy Iskandariy" and "Lison ut-tayr".

In the content of these epics, perfect human qualities are mainly interpreted from a philosophical point of view, and scientific and philosophical observations are also made on such issues as man and being, man and his psyche, man and nature, man and theology, man and his way of life.

Navoi's works reveal the logic of perfection, the solution to all the events in which a person is glorified as an integral part of this wonderful world, a miracle embodying all the features of the perfection of being. [3. Б. 76].

The creation of the Timurid State, which allowed the rapid development of religious and secular sciences, literature and art, also marked the beginning of a new type of Timurid renaissance. Undoubtedly, the interest of Amir Temur and the Temurids in theology, or rather mysticism, paved the way for the Naqshbandi sect to become a powerful ideological movement. Alisher Navoi worked during the heyday of the Timurid Empire.

As a statesman, Alisher Navoi supported the ideological teachings that determined the socio-spiritual life of society. Therefore, Navoi's works reflect the ideological foundations of the poet's worldview and creativity. While Eastern philosophy and mystical theory are based on the relationship between Allah, being and man, Alisher Navoi in his work sheds light on these issues through deep philosophical observation. In addition, in his works, the thinker seeks to illuminate society with the principles of humanism and to convey the issues of moral education through a philosophico-cognitive approach.

Such ideas as the love of life in mystical philosophy, the recognition of being a divine miracle and the appreciation of all its benefits are in tune with the work of Alisher Navoi on building a just society, promoting the principles of peace and tolerance.

Navoi is a great thinker and poet. He is a scientist who has deeply studied all the religious, philosophical and mystical teachings inherent to him. In "Nasoyim ul-Muhabbat" by Alisher Navoi, the poet notes that from a young age he talked a lot with mature sages of his time and proudly read the prayers received from them. Therefore, the role of interpretations and advice of mature thinkers of their time, Sufis and Hadith scholars in the formation of Alisher Navoi's worldview was incomparable. In this regard, it should be noted the special importance of the role of Abdurakhman Jami in the formation of the Navoi worldview. Such a conclusion can be drawn from the information given in Navoi's work "Hamsatul-mutahayyirin".

Alisher Navoi knew all the teachings he had created well enough and chose a moderate path in their presentation. Therefore, when analyzing and interpreting his works, it is advisable to take into account the reflection of various religious and philosophical teachings synthesized in his worldview.

The creativity of Alisher Navoi created works that embodied all the originally created religious ideas, great philosophies, their interpretations reflected in Persian and Turkic poetry, and enriched them with a new sensitivity. The scientific-artistic, religious-philosophical thinking reflected in the epics and gazelles of Navoi is so deep that in order to know the exact interpretation of some verses, special knowledge and skills are needed, as well as deep logical observation.

Comprehending the features of perfection in the legacy of Alisher Navoi, the acquisition of a profession and maturity from a young age are artistically interpreted in the epic "Farhod va Shirin". The image of Farhod, depicted in the rhythm of modern knowledge and moral education, personifies a perfect person who has mastered the necessary profession. [4. Б. 203].

According to Navoi, the period of a person's youth is the period of his most impeccable perfection, during which a person should have deep knowledge, education and profession. A person who has achieved perfection strives to radically reform society and develop it. In order to find your place in life, you also need to set a goal and understand the ways to achieve it. A perfect person should live in society as a creative person. Because man is the king of being, the most perfect being. Alisher Navoi vividly reveals the problem of human perfection in his works, and in his epic "Lison ut-tayr" he artistically comprehends that human perfection can be the basis for discovering the secrets of the universe and being. Navoi recognizes that among people only man is able to discover the secrets of the universe and being. The legacy of Navoi glorifies human enlightenment and the understanding of a perfect person on its basis. In all the images created in Navoi's work, the perfect man and his qualities of perfection are shown as an example. [5. Б. 16].

Observations show that the most common translation of the works of Alisher Navoi is "Majolis un-nafois". It has been translated into Persian several times. In this work, first of all, the merits of Sultan Muhammad Fakhriy (1521, Herat), Muhammad Kazvini (1532, Istanbul) and Shoali Abdullah (1598, Nishapur) should be mentioned. Research shows that this work of the poet was also translated in India. Abdulboki Sharif Vafo did this good deed. He successfully translated the work into Persian using a rare manuscript copied in 1491.

The discovery of copies of the usual collection of Alisher Navoi's textbook in the treasury of the Coma Research Center in Mumbai suggests that the poet's legacy could have been used as a textbook in school. The fact is that the work "Majolis un-nafois" is the site of Persian manuscripts from the Madras State Library of Oriental Manuscripts, the work "G'aroyib us-sig'ar" is a manuscript published in India, the work "Saddi Iskandariy" is kept in the library of the Usmania Institute in Hyderabad, consisting of an interpretation from the work of Muhiyiddin in Persian called "Favoyidi Alisheriy" gives us the real essence of Navoi's work in global level.

In the XVII century, the Georgian poet Nodar Tsitsiashvili created "Baramguriani" based on the epic of Alisher Navoi "Sabai Sayyor". The poet compares this epic of Navoi with the epic of Nazomi and Husrav Dehlaviy and consciously takes it as the basis of his future work. Just a cursory acquaintance with the work of Nodar Tsitsiashvili shows how much it is consonant with "Sabai Sayyor".

The rich heritage of Alisher Navoi is in the focus of attention not only of Eastern, but also of Western scientists. From the end of the 16th century to the beginning of the 17th century, Navoi's works were published 4 times in Italian and 5 times in German. Among them, translations into German of the works "Farhod va Shirin", "Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn", "Mahbub ul-qulub" should be noted. Scientists note that among these translations, the translation of A. Kurella's epic "Farhod va Shirin" differs in artistic height.

Appreciating the work of Navoi, the German scientist Alfred Kurella said: "The great innovator Goethe would give all his joy to the free spirit contained in the epics, shirts and epigrams of Navoi".

French orientalists have been interested in Navoi's heritage since the 19th century. French scientists S.De.Sacy, E. Quatremer, F. Belin and especially Louis Aragon took a wide part in the

study and popularization of Navoi's life and work. According to Louis Aragon, the literary heritage of Alisher Navoi has lived in the hearts of people for centuries and will continue to live.

According to the latest information, an English-language edition of Alisher Navoi's "Lison ut-tayr" is also being prepared, which marks the beginning of a new stage in the study of Navoi's creativity in the West. We can proudly say that the peoples of Europe also enjoy the rich world heritage of Alisher Navoi.

According to scientists, the magazine "Lettr" ("Literature"), published in English, German, French, Spanish, Polish, Hungarian, Czech and Slovak, is also actively engaged in the dissemination and popularization of Alisher Navoi's work among foreign readers.

Navoi humanity. He is a great artist who glorified the ideas of peace and enlightenment with great artistry, and a brilliant writer who managed to bring the language and literature of the Turkic peoples to the world stage. In this respect, he deserves a place among the brightest figures of world literature, Homer and Dante, Rudaki and Firdousi, Nizami and Saadi, Shakespeare and Balzac. The great Azerbaijani poet Fuzuli highly appreciated the work of Alisher Navoi and called him "Sultoni salotini shuaro". Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur: "Alisherbek naziri yo'q kishi erdi. Turkiy til bila to she'r aytibturlar, hech kim oncha ko'p va xo'b aytqon emas".

The rich heritage of the great Navoi is synonymous with all periods of human history. And the words of the immortal genius still support the good deeds of humanity.

The role of Navoi heritage in the spiritual development of the younger generation is incomparable. In the works of the thinker, such issues as respect for parents, teachers, elders, acquisition of knowledge, good morals, avoidance of evil are undoubtedly closely related to the idea of a perfect person, which has always been the poet's dream.

Alisher Navoi left a rich poetic, prose and scientific heritage, the volume of which was confirmed by the poet himself in the epic "Lison ut-tayr" with a volume of one hundred thousand bytes. Alisher Navoi's works have been translated into dozens of languages. Alisher Navoi is a thinker who brought Uzbek literature to the world with his rich heritage and founded the Uzbek literary language. The highest development of lyrical genres and epic in Uzbek literature is recognized by the name of Alisher Navoi. The perfect text of the Navoi heritage in the Uzbek language has been created. The complete collection of the poet's works in 10 volumes has been published. 10 volumes of Navoi's works have been published in Russian. As a result of continuous research on the collection, study and research of our cultural heritage, new manuscripts of the Navoi heritage have been discovered and put into scientific circulation. [8].

Alisher Navoi's works have recently been published in Chinese, Russian, his devans, his words of wisdom have been published in Persian, English, German, French, Spanish, Japanese and other languages, through the international publishing house "Alhudo" the work "Nazmul Javohir", written by Alisher Navoi in order to enjoy the proverbs of Hazrat Ali ibn Abu Talib in five languages in Iran, in the middle of this year Navoi's book "Farhod and Shirin", which will be published in Ukrainian, is a vivid example of the growing interest in heritage, Navoi has been left to us, and Navoi's world Heritage is of great importance. That is why these works, in particular, "Hamsa" have long attracted the attention of historians of the East and West, as well as representatives of other disciplines. [6. Б. 55].

More than five centuries have passed since the immortal works of this great thinker-poet, who embodied encyclopedic knowledge and took a worthy place in the treasury of world culture, serve a new generation. His rich and immense heritage has left us an invaluable contribution to the treasury of universal culture. They promoted noble ideas about a bright life. That is why Navoi's works are always in harmony with both space and time. Our poet wrote about the highest duty of a perfect man:

Odami ersang, demagil odami,
Oni kim yo'q xalq g'amidin g'ami.

In Navoi's work, love of life is imbued with such humanistic ideas as the glorification of human dignity, friendship, brotherhood, peace and harmony between peoples, regardless of nationality, race or religion. In particular, these brilliant teachings of the great Navoi, who foresaw interethnic conflicts taking place in different regions today, are consonant with all periods of human history:

Olam ahli bilingizkim, ish emas dushmannlig',
Yor o'lung bir-biringizgakim, erur yorlig' ish. [7. B. 249].

Full coverage of Navoi's life and work, the fact that Hamsa is a world-class encyclopedic work showing Navoi's great poetry, his contribution to the development of jurisprudence, literature and linguistics, his patronage of science and culture, as well as his independence. It is important that each of the Navoi scholars contributes to such an important matter as familiarizing the world community with the fact that the rich heritage becomes the spiritual heritage of the peoples of the world, the image of Navoi is glorified and the priceless heritage is studied.

Conclusion/Recommendations

In short, Alisher Navoi devoted his entire life and activity to the happiness of man, the well-being of his people. In the centuries of Navoi, such human values as faith, honesty, piety, generosity, mercy have always been glorified, and others were also encouraged. The annual large-scale celebration of Alisher Navoi's birthday in our country provides a basis for discovering new aspects of his life and work. The legacy of Alisher Navoi is a unique pearl in the history of Oriental literature. After all, the great scientific heritage of Alisher Navoi, in-depth study and popularization of Uzbek national culture form the basis of Navoi spirituality. Today, interest in the study of Navoi's creativity is growing day by day. Because the essence of the thinker's creativity is devoted to the interpretation of perfect human qualities.

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